

Design Optimization of a Heat-Pipe Microreactor Design using Bayesian Optimization

Cole Howard ^{1*}, Jason Hou¹

¹North Carolina State University, Raleigh, North Carolina

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ABSTRACT

This work presents a Bayesian optimization using the MIDAS framework for the neutronic design of a heat pipe microreactor using the Serpent Monte Carlo code. As the nuclear industry advances toward next-generation reactor concepts, such as compact, transportable microreactors, there is a growing need for systematic and efficient optimization methodologies to guide early-stage design. These reactors introduce novel design challenges, including unique geometries, alternative fuel and coolant materials, and nontraditional operational regimes, that demand advanced computational tools to identify optimal design configurations. To address this, we employ Bayesian optimization (BO) with Gaussian process (GP) surrogates, which efficiently approximate the reactor performance while adaptively selecting new design points. This approach minimizes the number of required Serpent evaluations while converging toward optimal design objectives, such as maximizing neutron economy, flattening power distribution, or meeting safety criteria. The results demonstrate that BO can effectively accelerate the neutronic design process while maintaining accuracy, providing a powerful framework for exploring large, nonlinear design spaces in advanced reactor development. This work highlights the critical role of probabilistic and machine learning-based optimization in enabling the rapid, systematic, and informed design of emerging nuclear technologies.

Keywords: Bayesian Optimization, Gaussian Process, Microreactor, MIDAS

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of advanced nuclear reactor technologies is critical to meeting the growing global demand for safe, reliable, and low-carbon energy. Among these innovations, microreactors offer unique advantages for remote power generation, emergency deployment, and grid resilience [1]. However, the novel geometries, alternative fuel and coolant configurations, and nontraditional operational regimes of these reactors introduce complex neutronic behavior, making design optimization challenging. Traditional methods, such as exhaustive parametric studies or heuristic trial-and-error approaches, are computationally expensive and often inefficient for exploring the large and nonlinear design spaces inherent to these systems.

Bayesian optimization has emerged as a promising strategy for efficiently navigating high-dimensional and expensive-to-evaluate design spaces [2]. By employing probabilistic surrogate models like Gaussian processes, Bayesian optimization can intelligently balance exploration of unknown regions with exploitation of promising configurations, enabling designers to identify optimal reactor parameters, such as core geometry, fuel composition, and moderation, using a minimal number of expensive simulations. This approach is particularly well-suited to neutronic design studies using tools such as Serpent, where each simulation can require significant computational resources. Bayesian optimization not only accelerates convergence toward optimal configurations but also provides uncertainty estimates that inform design decisions.

*cahowar9@ncsu.edu

In this work, we apply Bayesian optimization to the neutronic design of a heat pipe microreactor using Serpent [3] simulations, demonstrating the potential to systematically improve performance while reducing computational cost. The optimization is facilitated through the Modularly Integrated Design Assistance Suite (MIDAS) [4], which streamlines the integration of simulation evaluations and surrogate modeling. This study highlights the growing importance of probabilistic, data-driven optimization methodologies for advanced reactor development, providing a framework for efficiently exploring and improving novel reactor concepts.

2. MODULARLY INTEGRATED DESIGN ASSISTANCE SUITE FRAMEWORK

The Modularly Integrated Design Assistance Suite (MIDAS) framework is a computational python-based framework originally developed to automate and accelerate reactor core loading pattern optimization or lattice optimization through the use of select optimization algorithms and interfacing with various physics solvers [4].

In this project, MIDAS is extended beyond traditional core loading applications to address generalized reactor design optimization problems. Rather than optimizing only discrete loading configurations, the framework is adapted to continuous and hybrid design variables governing overall reactor performance.

2.1. Bayesian Optimization

The application of probabilistic surrogate-based optimization, particularly Bayesian optimization (BO), has grown significantly in engineering and expensive simulation domains. Survey papers underline BO's strength in navigating black-box functions that are expensive to evaluate, non-convex, and often lack analytically tractable derivatives [5]. Due to its promise in literature, Bayesian Optimization is the newest addition to the MIDAS framework.

In engineering design contexts, BO has been used for multi-objective, mixed variable, and high-fidelity simulation studies. A benchmarking study in fluid dynamics demonstrates that BO can find suitable solutions in only a small number of evaluations of expensive simulations [6], underscoring its practicality for real-world phenomena [7].

Within nuclear and reactor design applications, BO has also begun to see traction. For example, a recent conference study demonstrated BO's feasibility for neutronic core design of a homogeneous two-region core. The authors reported that BO could reach near-optimal solutions in fewer simulations compared to brute-force approaches [8]. Another work applied constrained BO in the context of criticality experiments using high-fidelity Monte Carlo transport codes, indicating the method's relevance for reactor neutronics and safety-centred design [9].

Bayesian Optimization (BO) is a surrogate model-based sequential framework to optimize expensive or black-box functions $f(\mathbf{x})$ that are expensive to evaluate or lack analytic gradients. The goal is to efficiently approximate the global optimum:

$$\mathbf{x}^* = \arg \min_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}} f(\mathbf{x}), \quad (1)$$

where each evaluation of $f(\mathbf{x})$, such as a Serpent Monte Carlo neutronics simulation, may require significant computational resources. In this project, we will demonstrate the use of BO, where the black box function we are attempting to learn is the fitness function, constructed by output parameters calculated by Serpent. Each evaluation will take an input of a unique set of design parameters to test.

2.1.1. Gaussian Process Surrogate

At the core of BO lies a probabilistic surrogate model, most commonly a Gaussian Process (GP), which defines a distribution over functions such that any finite set of function values is jointly Gaussian:

$$f(\mathbf{x}) \sim \mathcal{GP}(m(\mathbf{x}), k(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')), \quad (2)$$

where $m(\mathbf{x})$ is the mean function and $k(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$ is the covariance (kernel) function encoding smoothness and correlation between points.

Given observations $\mathcal{D}_n = \{(\mathbf{x}_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^n$, the posterior predictive distribution at a new point \mathbf{x}_* has mean and variance:

$$\mu_n(\mathbf{x}_*) = \mathbf{k}_*^\top (K + \sigma^2 I)^{-1} \mathbf{y}, \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_n^2(\mathbf{x}_*) = k(\mathbf{x}_*, \mathbf{x}_*) - \mathbf{k}_*^\top (K + \sigma^2 I)^{-1} \mathbf{k}_*, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{k}_* = [k(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_*), \dots, k(\mathbf{x}_n, \mathbf{x}_*)]^\top$ and K is the kernel matrix.

2.1.2. Acquisition Functions

The next point to evaluate is determined by maximizing an *acquisition function* $\alpha(\mathbf{x}; \mathcal{D}_n)$, which quantifies the expected utility of evaluating f at \mathbf{x} . Common acquisition functions include:

Expected Improvement (EI):

$$\alpha_{\text{EI}}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbb{E}[\max(f_{\min} - f(\mathbf{x}), 0)] = (f_{\min} - \mu_n(\mathbf{x}))\Phi(z) + \sigma_n(\mathbf{x})\phi(z), \quad (5)$$

where $f_{\min} = \min_i y_i$, $z = \frac{f_{\min} - \mu_n(\mathbf{x})}{\sigma_n(\mathbf{x})}$, and $\Phi(\cdot)$, $\phi(\cdot)$ are the standard normal CDF and PDF, respectively. This takes into account both the probability that a sample \mathbf{x} will outperform the current best observation, and the statistically expected difference between the sample \mathbf{x} and the current best observation.

Probability of Improvement (PI):

$$\alpha_{\text{PI}}(\mathbf{x}) = \Phi\left(\frac{f_{\min} - \mu_n(\mathbf{x})}{\sigma_n(\mathbf{x})}\right), \quad (6)$$

which measures the probability that a sample at \mathbf{x} will outperform the current best observation.

Upper Confidence Bound (UCB):

$$\alpha_{\text{UCB}}(\mathbf{x}) = \mu_n(\mathbf{x}) - \kappa \sigma_n(\mathbf{x}), \quad (7)$$

where κ is a tunable parameter that controls the exploration–exploitation balance.

These acquisition functions naturally balance exploration (sampling where uncertainty $\sigma_n(\mathbf{x})$ is high) and exploitation (sampling near predicted minima $\mu_n(\mathbf{x})$).

2.2. General Optimization Workflow

In all optimization algorithms within MIDAS, an initial set of samples is generated. In MIDAS, it is possible to either generate random initial samples, or to define seed solutions which have better performance than random solutions and randomly perturb them to create different variations. Next, these

initial points must be evaluated. In the case of our optimization, we will create a fitness value to serve as the output of the evaluation function. The fitness function creates a unitless value which is a linear combination of the designer's chosen output parameters to consider in the optimization and weights which represent each parameter's importance to the overall design. Once the fitness has been calculated, in the case of BO, the GP surrogate will create a new posterior distribution based on the incoming samples and associated fitness values. Now, the acquisition function will be maximized over the new posterior distribution in order to find the next points to sample. Then, these samples will be evaluated, and the process will repeat until the optimization reaches its maximum number of iterations or other stopping criteria. This process can be seen in figure 1.

Figure 1. Generic Bayesian Optimization Flowchart

This process allows BO to efficiently explore complex design spaces by strategically allocating computational resources toward the most informative regions of the parameter space. When applied to reactor design problems, this workflow ensures that only the most promising Serpent simulations are executed, significantly reducing total computational cost while maintaining high optimization accuracy.

3. HEAT-PIPE MICROREACTOR DESIGN

For this project, we will base our work on the MRAD heat-pipe microreactor (HPMR) design created by Argonne National Laboratory (ANL) on the open-source virtual test bed [10, 11]. It was originally created by ANL to combine different microreactor technologies that traditional codes cannot properly simulate in order to demonstrate the use of new methods. The HPMR has a power of 2 MWth and is fueled with prismatic TRISO fuel in UCO form with a 40% packing fraction in a graphite matrix. It is comprised of 30 hexagonal assemblies, containing fuel pins, heat pipes, and moderator pins. These

moderator pins are made of YH_2 as to increase the slowing down power. The core has a height of 200 cm, with 160 cm of active fuel length and 20 cm on either side of beryllium metal reflector. Outside of the hexagonal assemblies lie a ring of hexagonal beryllium reflectors and 12 control drums. The control drums are largely filled of reflective beryllium, but have a surface of neutron absorbing material rotated outwards, which can be used to control reactivity by rotating this surface to face the core. By rotating these drums inward through the serpent model, we can evaluate whether or not a design's control drums would be able to create subcriticality. At the base design, we estimate a k_{eff} of 0.94212 ± 0.00028 , indicating that the initial design is more than capable of causing a reactor shutdown with only the control drums. It should be noted that a realistic design may incorporate a central control rod or other reactivity control system which would further ensure the ability to reach shutdown. The geometry of this model can be seen in figures 2a and 2b. Note that temperatures for fuel and moderator were used based on the original design[10], using an operating fuel temperature of 843.5 Kelvin for the fuel and triso particles, and a temperature of 842.16 Kelvin for the moderator. Due to a lack of thermal-hydraulic calculations in this project, the same temperatures were assumed during optimization. However, it should be noted that updated temperatures may significantly affect results, and would need to be evaluated with a thermal-hydraulic software package or multiphysics framework.

Figure 2. Side-by-side views of HPMR

For this optimization, we will look at the input parameters listed in table I, and use output parameters listed in table II. We will perturb pin radius, pin pitch, reflector thickness, fuel length, and fuel enrichment over the course of this optimization. These are basic components of the reactor design itself which can have significant impacts on the system neutronics. In addition, for evaluation of the reactor performance, we will be considering the radial power peaking factor, doppler temperature coefficient, reactor mass, cycle cost, k_{eff} at beginning of cycle, and cycle length as constraints and objectives. These serve to demonstrate that a user may take into account various required safety parameters or economic objectives, applicable for any reactor technology with its own set of specific safety requirements. For example, ensuring a reactor meets peaking factor limits or reactivity coefficients is essential to reactor design. In the case of a microreactor, since it likely needs to be transported, there may be a weight limit on the mode of transportation. Additionally, k_{eff} must be greater than 1.0 at BOC in order for a design

to be feasible, so this constraint has been included. All simulations and computations were performed on the Hazel high performance computer cluster at NC State university. Each serpent simulation used 65 CPU cores in parallel, and each run was completed in approximately 2 hours.

Table I. Optimization Design Parameters

Parameter	Range of Values to be Considered	Nominal Value
Pin Pitch (cm)	2.3-4.0	2.3
Fuel Pin Radius (cm)	0.5-2.3	1.0
Moderator Pin Radius (cm)	0.5-2.3	1.0
Axial Reflector Thickness (cm)	10-30	20
Active Fuel Length (cm)	120-200	160
Enrichment (wt %)	15-19.95	19.95

Table II. Optimization Objectives and Constraints

Output Parameter	Target or Goal	Nominal Value
$F_{\Delta H}$	Less than 1.40	1.28
Beginning of Cycle K_{eff}	Above 1.0	1.02004
Doppler Temperature Coefficient (pcm/k)	Less than 0	-2.283
Reactor Mass (lbs)	Less than 50,000	29,395.5
Cycle Cost (\$)	Minimize	14.5 M
Cycle Length (EFPD)	Above 1461	1555

Over the course of this optimization, we will seek to maximize the fitness value of our prospective solutions. The fitness value is a unitless value which represents the performance of a solution. In MIDAS, we define higher fitness values as being associated with a better solution and vice versa. In equation 8 below, the fitness function for our problem is defined.

$$\begin{aligned}
 F(x) = & 800 \cdot \min(0, F_{\Delta H} - 1.40) + 1 \cdot \max(0, 1461 - \text{EFPD}) \\
 & - 10^{-6} \cdot \text{cycle_cost} + 1 \cdot \max(0, 50000 - \text{tot_mass}) \\
 & + 100 \cdot \min(0, \alpha_{\text{doppler}}) + 800 \cdot \max(0, 1 - k_{\text{eff}})
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

With initial optimization results, we were able to find promising designs. In tables III and IV respectively, performance parameters and design parameters of the optimized model can be seen in comparison to the limits and nominal values.

Table III. Optimization Results

Output Parameter	Target or Goal	Nominal Value	Optimized Model Value
$F_{\Delta H}$	Less than 1.40	1.28	1.39
Beginning of Cycle K_{eff}	Above 1.0	1.02004	1.03861
Doppler Temperature Coefficient (pcm/k)	Less than -2.0	-2.283	-2.624
Reactor Mass (lbs)	Less than 50,000	29,395.5	39,291.6
Cycle Cost (\$)	Minimize	14.5 M	15.2 M
Cycle Length (EFPD)	Above 1461	1555	3634

As we can see, the reactor has gained more reactivity, seen by the increase in peaking and criticality. This is likely due to the introduction of more mass, seen in the increase in fuel height, increased moderator

Table IV. Optimized Design Parameters

Parameter	Range of Values to be Considered	Nominal Value	Optimized Model
Pin Pitch (cm)	2.3-4.0	2.3	2.33
Fuel Pin Radius (cm)	0.5-2.3	1.0	0.98
Moderator Pin Radius (cm)	0.5-2.3	1.0	1.86
Axial Reflector Thickness (cm)	10-30	20	26.12
Active Fuel Length (cm)	120-200	160	178.59
Enrichment (wt %)	15-19.95	19.95	19.25

pin radius, reflector thickness, and total reactor mass. We can also see that the reactor cycle cost has become about \$700,000 USD more expensive as compared to the base model, likely due to the increased fuel height. However, the cycle length has also increased by over an additional 2000 EFPD, bringing the cycle length from approximately 4.25 years to 10 years.

In figure 3, we can see a comparison of the neutron spectra between the base model and the optimized model. In figure 3, we can see that the two models, as expected, have similar neutron spectra, as seen in the similar shape and near identical fast flux. However, the optimized model seems to have a lower epithermal flux and notably higher thermal flux. This can likely be attributed to the increased moderator pin radius, which would increase the slowing down power inside the model. Additionally, by rotating the control drums inward on the optimized design, we find a k_{eff} of 0.96990 ± 0.00026 , indicating that, while the beginning of cycle k_{eff} is higher than the base design, the optimized design is still more than capable of shutdown with only the control drums. Furthermore, we can see the optimization performance below in figure 4. Based on this it seems that our optimization is performing as intended, continually testing and finding new solutions, slowly improving the best known solution as the GP surrogate better learns the fitness function shape.

Figure 3. Neutron Spectrum Comparison between Base and Optimized Model

Figure 4. Optimization Performance over Generations

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrates the successful application of Bayesian optimization within the MIDAS framework to the neutronic design of a heat-pipe microreactor modeled using the Serpent Monte Carlo code. By leveraging Gaussian process surrogate modeling and acquisition-based sequential sampling, the optimization process efficiently explored a high-dimensional, nonlinear design space. The approach iden-

tified promising design modifications, such as increased moderator radius, extended fuel height, and thicker reflectors, that collectively improved key performance metrics, including Doppler temperature feedback, cycle length, and beginning-of-cycle reactivity.

The results highlight several important findings. First, Bayesian optimization can systematically guide reactor designers toward feasible and high-performing configurations while avoiding the inefficiency of brute-force parameter sweeps. Second, the GP surrogate effectively captured complex relationships between geometric inputs and neutronic outputs, enabling informed exploration and convergence toward improved solutions. Third, the optimized design illustrates the inherent trade-offs in microreactor engineering, notably increases in reactivity and cycle length were achieved at the cost of higher mass and slightly increased cycle cost.

Overall, this study demonstrates that probabilistic, machine-learning-based optimization tools such as Bayesian optimization offer a powerful and practical methodology for advanced reactor development. As next-generation microreactor concepts continue to evolve, the ability to intelligently navigate large design spaces using data-driven, uncertainty-aware algorithms will be essential. Future work will extend this effort to incorporate multi-objective formulations, multiphysics coupling, and additional thermal-hydraulic design parameters and criteria.

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